

Archaeoastronomy and the study of Chinese Town Planning, Architectures and Monuments

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna
Politecnico di Torino

Here the list of my papers on Chinese town planning, architectures and monuments, that I made in the framework of archaeoastronomical studies, and to find possible alignments to sunrise on solstices. In particular, the result obtained in 2012 for the mausoleum of Li Hong (formally Emperor Xiaojing) of Tang near Goushi in Henan, is here discussed again. The Tang Dynasty was a dynasty that ruled during the VII-VIII centuries CE. The mausoleum of the Emperor is a large pyramid with a flat top; near it we find a small pyramid for Empress Ai. The two pyramids are inked by the sunrise on winter solstice.

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Here some notes about my papers on Chinese town planning, architectures and monuments, which I investigated in the framework of archaeoastronomical studies. "Sunrise and Sunset Azimuths in the Planning of Ancient Chinese Towns" [1] is considering the planning of ancient Chinese towns. In the planning of them we can see an evident orientation with the cardinal direction north-south. However, other features reveal a possible orientation with the directions of sunrise and sunset on solstices too, as in the case of Shangdu (Xanadu), the summer capital of Kublai Khan. In [1] we discussed some other examples of a possible solar orientation in the planning of the ancient towns of Xi'an, Khanbalik and Dali. "A Solar Orientation in the Town-Planning of Xanadu" [2] is discussing the case of Xanadu (Shangdu), that was the summer capital of Kublai Khan. The town was planned by the architect Liu Bingzhong (1216-1274), the Kublai's adviser who suggested the development of a new and more precise calendar. The ruins of Xanadu seem to have a planning of the walls according to a solar orientation at sunrise/sunset on solstices.

However, my first paper about the Chinese monuments was on the pyramids.

"The Chinese Pyramids and the Sun" [3] is discussing them. The Chinese Pyramids are huge ancient burial mounds. In the satellite images we can see some complexes where the main buildings are the pyramidal mounds of an emperor and his empress. In [3], it was discussed a possible sunrise/sunset orientation of some of these pairs of pyramids, on solstices and equinoxes. A very interesting case is that of the mausoleum of Li Hong (Emperor Xiaojing) of Tang Dynasty near Goushi, Henan. The Tang Dynasty ruled during the VII-VIII centuries CE.

Here some useful links, as given on 5 January 2018.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chinese_pyramids

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chinese_pyramids#Mausoleum_of_Emperor_Xiaojing_of_Tang_near_Goushi,_Henan

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Li_Hong

The large pyramid with the flat top that we can see in the Figure 1 is that of the emperor, and near it there is the pyramid of Empress Ai. In [3], I shown some simulations of the sunrise/sunset directions on solstice at this monumental complex, obtained by means of sollumis.com software.

Here I show a new simulation, using the direction of sunrise on summer solstice as given by another software.

The result in shown in the Figure 1. The yellow line is the direction of sunrise on summer solstice. The pivot is given at the geometric centre of the base of the pyramid. This image is obtained from a screenshot of software SunCalc.org, which is a remarkable tool and help for archaeoastronomical studies. This software uses ESRI maps. On them, it is based ESRI GIS (more information at <https://www.esri.com/en-us/home>).

From the satellite image we can see an alignment of the two pyramids within a degree. It is not necessary to consider a difference between astronomical and natural horizon, because the site is on a large flat plane. The fact that, during the centuries, the declination of the sun slightly changed of about 0.1 degrees, is not considered here. Its effect is smaller than the uncertainty that we have because of the choice of the centre of the pyramids' basements.

Figure 1: The pyramid of Li Hong (Emperor Xiaojing) of Tang Dynasty near Goushi, Henan. The small pyramid of the Empress Ai. The yellow line is the direction of sunrise on summer solstice. The pivot is given at the geometric centre of the base of the pyramid. This image is obtained from a screenshot of software SunCalc.org, which is a remarkable tool and help for archaeoastronomical studies. This software uses ESRI maps. On them, it is based ESRI GIS (more information at <https://www.esri.com/en-us/home>)

The fact that the axis of the Emperor's pyramid is not perfectly aligned along N-S direction could have been a consequence of a survey based on the use of magnetic compasses.

"Magnetic Compasses and Chinese Architectures" [4] is a paper in which it is discussed the effect of the use of magnetic compasses on the orientation of ancient Chinese architectonic complexes.

As Czech researchers proposed in 2011 [5,6], assuming these complexes ideally oriented by the ancient architects along north-south direction, in the case that the surveys were made by means of magnetic compasses, we can find the axes of the complexes deviating from the cardinal direction, according to the local magnetic declination that existed at the time the structures were built. Following this idea, in [4] I discussed some examples of possible alignments obtained by means of magnetic compasses, concluding that the Chinese surveyors adopted, during the Ming dynasty, a method based on the magnetic compasses. However, the architects of the old Yuan Dynasty used an astronomical method for sure.

Let me continue illustrating my paper "The road to the Loulan Kingdom" [7]. It is a discussion on an ancient kingdom along the Silk Road, and some observations based on satellite images.

References [8-14] are some articles which are also discussing the Chinese architectures in the framework of archaeoastronomy.

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